

OPPORTUNITIES FOR USING MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING PROFESSIONAL ENGLISH

Nuritdinova Yarkinoy Abdulkhoshim kizi

Lecturer of department of foreign languages, faculty of agro engineering and hydro melioration, Andijan Institute of Agriculture and Agro technologies

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Abstract: The article defines multimedia technologies and explains the possibilities of their use in teaching professional English. The author defines the main tasks, principles and sequence of using multimedia technologies. The article outlines the main advantages of multimedia, such as: development of cognitive skills, activation of students' cognitive activity, relevance of the material studied, the possibility of distance learning. The author also noted the shortcomings of the technology, which mainly consist in the limited material resource and providing educational institutions with equipment.

Key words: Communication, multimedia, media, professional foreign language, presentation, students.

The study of professional foreign languages by university students necessitates a total change in the higher education system. In order to improve the access of students and future professionals to foreign sources, learning English is extremely necessary. The latest methods of teaching foreign languages, in particular professional directions in universities, determine the interactivity of such training and the use of the latest technologies, namely: multimedia tools. Determining the specifics of implementing multimedia technologies in teaching professionally directed English to medical students will help improve the quality of Education.

In particular, the use of multimedia technologies in teaching university students a professionally directed foreign language was studied by M. Petkova, G. Sumina, M. Tukalo, S. Filipenko. Outstanding Russian teachers: I Zyazyun, S. Nikolaeva, O. Pometun studied the interactivity of learning at universities and paid considerable attention to multimedia learning. Ukrainian methodologists L. Bulat, N. Didyk, A. Zorika, studying the peculiarities of teaching professional English, noted the need to use multimedia technologies (player, PC, multimedia board), motivating this by the need to activate students' cognitive activity. Modern authors define Multimedia in different ways: for example, L. Shannikova defines multimedia training as training on the use of information presentation on various media: audio, video, and interactive tasks [8]. It is noted that it is necessary to use appropriate software that will allow you to mutually link links,

create hyperlinks, provide multi-layered educational material, and, accordingly, compare training [2].

In connection with the urgent need to study the issue of studying technologies for improving the teaching of English to students, the author formulated the research topic: features of using multimedia tools for learning professionally directed English to students.

The purpose of the study is to formulate the concept of “multimedia means of teaching English”, to determine these means that can be used in the study of Medical English, to determine the basic principles of using the means, to analyze the main disadvantages and advantages of multimedia means, as well as to give practical examples of using multimedia means.

Modern authors define Multimedia in different ways: for example, L. Shannikova defines multimedia training as training on the use of information presentation on various media: audio, video and interactive tasks that require technical support by a player or personal computer [8]. A group of authors notes the need to use appropriate software that will allow you to mutually link links, create hyperlinks, provide multi-layered educational material, and, accordingly, compare training [2]. The use of G.I. Links provides the student with complete information about the material being studied, as well as the possibility of deepening the study, and differentiating learning by degree [7]. So, a student who meets an unfamiliar concept in a text or audio fragment can click on a hyperlink and get a text, audio or video presentation of the material. At the same time, it is possible to continue training without detailing the incomprehensible. According to the author's personal experience, multimedia training can cover the use of multimedia textbooks with software developed for them, the use of medical materials on the Internet, encyclopedic material, the use and creation of presentations, joint work in a hum document, the use of audio and video equipment, multimedia whiteboards, work with students within the Wi-Fi network.

The purpose of using multimedia technologies is to humanize education, increase the effectiveness of training and professional development of the student, in particular within the framework of mastering a foreign language of a professional direction.

The tasks of using multimedia tools in teaching medical students English are the study of professional lexical material; teaching writing, maintaining medical documentation online; studying grammatical constructions inherent in

medical texts, using the example of cases; training the perception of Professional English by ear and pronunciation training when working with video fragments.

General multimedia applications that students can use can be classified as follows:

- combining terms with synonyms, images, definitions, on a tablet or computer screen;
- discussing certain phenomena, adding links to illustrations, video and audio fragments, working with a tablet, mobile phone, electronic whiteboard;
- GoogleDoc - creating a single interactive document on the Google platform with shared access for the entire group; with the ability to add audio and Video, Comment. That is, for example, a document dedicated to the topic "infectious respiratory diseases" will contain theoretical information on anatomy and physiology, typology of diseases, audio and video fragments, crosswords and other tasks compiled by the teacher and students. The document can take the form of a shared chat, with corrections and the ability to delete comments.

Now there are numerous programs for learning foreign languages of a general direction, from foreign publishers, in particular, the Grammar in Use multimedia disc by O. Swan, English Grammar in use by R. Murphy, as well as free access to educational programs published by Oxford University Press, Cambridge University Press. The above-mentioned publishers post their own materials on the site, where, after entering the Access Key, students get access to various audio and video fragments on medical topics.

According to the analysis of methodological sources and the author's own experience, an approximate scheme for conducting a multimedia lesson using a laptop was formed (in compliance with the sequence of teaching vocabulary, grammar, reading, writing, listening and speaking):

Systematization of what you have learned and verification of tasks (using a video presentation). It is optimal -- when each student is provided with a separate PC, on which he makes a short test task to fill out or combine, which is automatically checked by the computer. If there is only 1 computer, the teacher shows the students the passage and discusses it with everyone.

Introduction of new vocabulary, by presenting a presentation, audio files or video files, with illustrations of terminology, and the following task on the screen: tasks for choosing the correct pronunciation or translation, tasks for

combining, tasks “compose a word”. Additionally, students use the vocabulary presented at the level of “word - phrase”. The pinning exercise can use “fill in the blanks” in the text on the screen.

Reading new text and next work. Students are shown a piece of text (preferably a projector) for a certain period (1.5-3 minutes.), with new vocabulary, after which they must perform post-text exercises (to supplement sentences, define headings to the text, fill in spaces with missing words to choose from).

Presentation of grammatical material used in the text. The teacher should choose the content of texts (if the teacher does not adhere to the developed course of the publishing house) in such a way that students consistently get acquainted with all the constructions: Verb Tenses, conditions, Modal verbs but the focus of the lesson is not on grammar. Students are offered tasks to fill in gaps or choose the correct version of the sentence.

Listening exercises. Students are offered a fragment of text or dialogue related to the topic being taught, followed by testing their understanding of statements (correct or incorrect, choose the correct statements, arrange the statements in order, and add missing information).

Monologue and dialogical speaking. It is optimal to use audio recording programs, followed by checking tasks by a teacher or group, but if the time resource is limited, it is possible to present samples of utterances to students, inviting them to create similar ones of their own.

The analysis of literary sources and the author's own experience contributed to the determination of the main advantages of using multimedia in the educational process: activation of cognitive activity through direct motivation of students; formation of cognitive processes among students, as well as skills of collective interaction; selection of only relevant topics for training and expansion of educational material with the latest information; availability of information and the possibility of Correction of material; the possibility of correspondence work, which does not limit students to the need for physical presence in the classroom. However, this method also contains disadvantages: the high cost of multimedia equipment and limited resources, psychological rejection of the method by teachers who have not mastered computer technology and use traditional training.

Conclusions and prospects of the study. The author defined multimedia technologies as the use of audio or video fragments recorded on digital media, presented to students from the screen of a PC, laptop, multimedia board and

determine the possibility of interaction of students with the learning environment. Teaching medical students professional English requires the use of multimedia tools to familiarize them with international sources of information.

Multimedia training contributes to activation of cognitive activity, intensive development of cognitive processes in students and development of teamwork skills, relevance of training, availability of information, opportunities for distance learning of students.

Multimedia technologies are used for teaching lexical and grammatical material, as well as teaching and controlling reading, writing, speaking, and listening.

The main advantages of multimedia training are the relevance of information, accessibility of the presented material and personal development of the student through the educational environment.

The main disadvantages of the method are the limited material resources and the inability to provide all classrooms and all students with technical equipment, the inability of teachers to work with computer technologies and the personal bias towards such training of both students and teachers, due to the classicality of teaching. We consider it promising to conduct a comparative analysis of the success of teaching professional English using the multimedia method and the classical method in groups of students and doctors who are preparing to pass a foreign professional exam in English.

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